

**LEADERSHIP PRACTICES OF DEPARTMENT HEADS AND TEACHERS
ENGAGEMENT OF JHS TEACHERS IN SELECTED PRIVATE SCHOOL
IN GUMACA, QUEZON: BASIS FOR PROFESSIONAL
DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 27

Issue 6

Pages: 574-588

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2586

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14035160

Manuscript Accepted: 10-05-2024

Leadership Practices of Department Heads and Teachers Engagement of JHS Teachers in Selected Private School in Gumaca, Quezon: Basis for Professional Development Program

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Abstract

The study investigated the leadership practices of Department Heads and Teachers' Engagement of JHS teachers in Selected Private Schools in Gumaca, Quezon, to come up with a Basis for Professional Development Program. The study was designed using a descriptive method. The Junior High School teachers participated in the study. A questionnaire was utilized as the main data-gathering tool. This study revealed that the leadership practices of the respondents towards selected department heads were excellent as employed or applied in the schools. This is reflected in innovative leaders, where the department heads have the abilities and qualities to push for innovation in the activity field of the organization. When it comes to Charismatic Leaders, the department heads seize new opportunities in order to achieve goals. And, as referred to by Command and Control Leaders, the department heads apply to all subsets of an enterprise, to the functions performed, to the levels of organizations, and to the focus of the activity, whether strategic or tactical. In addition, the leadership practices of the department heads have an excellent impact on teachers' engagement and motivation, as can be observed in the school performance. This can be inferred to Unity of Purpose where the school mission provides a clear sense of direction for teachers, teachers understand the school's mission, and the school mission statement reflects the values of the community. Along with Collegial Support, it indicated that teachers are willing to help out whenever there is a problem and that other teachers value teachers' ideas. In terms of professional development, it is exemplified that teachers regularly seek ideas from seminars, colleagues, and conferences and that the faculty values professional development. Lastly, in general, there is no significant relationship between leadership practices and the impacts of leadership practices on teachers' engagement and motivation. However, each leadership practice has at least one but at most five of the teachers' engagement indicators exhibiting a significant relationship between leadership practices and their impacts on teachers' engagement and motivation.

Keywords: *digital, learning material, 2D animation, drafting technology*

Introduction

Effective teachers are recognized as the cornerstone of quality education, impacting student learning outcomes significantly. To equip teachers with the necessary knowledge, skills, and practices, teacher professional development (PD) has become a critical focus for educational systems globally. However, the effectiveness of PD hinges on various factors, with growing emphasis placed on the crucial role of school leadership in shaping its success. While research acknowledges a positive link between strong principal leadership and improved teacher engagement, implementation of learned skills, and, ultimately, higher student achievement, the specific mechanisms through which this influence operates still need to be explored. This study delves into this gap by investigating the impact of principal leadership practices on teacher PD and student success.

The quantitative analysis examines the correlations between specific principal leadership practices identified through the surveys and teacher self-reported engagement in PD and student achievement data. Based on the interviews, the qualitative analysis explores the lived experiences of principals and teachers, providing deeper insights into how specific leadership practices translate into concrete support for PD and ultimately influence student learning.

Effective leadership is necessary for the advancement of teachers as well as society. In the technological advancement of the 21st century, there are many challenges to compete with, including worldwide teacher networks, which demand a great educational leader for educational institutions. There are three main aspects of a principal's leadership in dealing with educational and cultural reforms: increasing participation, transferring vision, and producing change. Their competencies value the effectiveness of leaders in the educational sector to contribute to improving the quality of education in the era of technological advancement (Sungtong, 2007; Abbas et al., 2020).

Leadership is particularly important in educational administration because of its far-reaching effects on accomplishing school programs, objectives, and attainment of educational goals (Peretomode, 1991). Educational leadership refers to the leadership that provides direction and expert advice on the development of learning, teaching, and curriculum, emphasizes relevance to education in management, diagnoses educational problems, and encourages professional development and teaching improvement (Cheng, 1994). The significance of educational leadership is due to the belief that leadership quality makes a major difference in school and student outcomes. There is also increasing recognition that schools require effective leaders to provide the best possible education for their learners (Ibukun, 1997). Educational leaders worldwide search for ways to grow schools as learning centers that can effectively nurture and sustain the development of students. Leadership that supports student learning is critically important in this process.

The main job of a principal is to assist in leading, directing, and coordinating various activities inside the school. The primary

responsibility of the principal is to create and sustain an excellent teaching-learning environment for the educational programs running in the school. The principal is also responsible for supporting the teachers in their teaching practices. Principals have a critical role in achieving the institution's goals and objectives. Among these responsibilities, principals must give genuine and effective leadership, improving teachers' professional presentation. The principal is responsible for giving highly valued visions that are focused on their day-to-day methods and that foster a good culture that supports exceptional teacher performance (Nanson, 2010; Saleem et al., 2020).

In various locations and circumstances, a lot of researchers explained leadership such as describes leadership as “a specific attitude adopted by a leader toward his or her subordinates to motivate them to achieve the organization's objectives and goals. It states that leadership is recognized as the abilities and practical skills of the persons, groups, or organizations to lead, influence, or provide guidance to other persons, teams, or the whole organization.

The quality of basic education in the Philippines has improved since the start of the new millennium, but public schools in the country continue to face a multitude of challenges. Developments in access to education and in soft and hard infrastructure have ameliorated certain school conditions. For instance, kindergarten enrollment almost doubled from 2008 to 2014, and the proportion of school-age children attending basic education also increased. Student-teacher ratio in public high schools improved from 38:1 in 2010 to 29:1 in 2013, while student-classroom ratio fell from 64:1 in 2010 to 47:1 in 2013 (World Bank, 2016). Dropout rates decreased from 6.29% in the school year (SY) 2010-2011 to 2.70% in SY 2015- 2016 at the elementary level and from 7.79% to 6.65% at the secondary level in the same period (NEDA, 2017). In spite of these achievements, public schools still suffer from poor basic infrastructure and facilities, Absenteeism of teachers particularly in highly urbanized cities, lack of operational funding and professional development opportunities for school teachers, and limited support from the local government (World Bank, 2016). For example, in SY 2014-2015, the student-classroom ratio was higher than the national average of 1:34 at elementary level and 1:48 at secondary level in Region IV-A (1:41 and 1:52), Bicol Region (1:35 and 1:41), Davao Region (1:41 and 1:46), Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (ARMM) (1:49 and 1:55). National Capital Region (NCR) (1:70 and 1:60). Absenteeism is more of a problem in highly urbanized cities where almost one in 10 teachers was absent in 2014, which is 54% higher than the national average. With regard to the national government's budget allocation, elementary and high schools received only Php448 of the Php581 allocated for each student for student appropriations as part of the maintenance and other operating expenses (MOOE) of the schools (World Bank, 2016).

Furthermore, Phuc et al. (2021) also found that a leadership style refers to a leader's style of giving directions, implementing plans, and motivating followers. Among others, a leader uses a different style of leadership, depending on the situation. In situations of emergency, an autocratic style of leadership is considered more effective, while for a highly motivated and aligned team, democratic or laissez-faire styles are recognized as more effective.

Despite the fact that leadership is an essential characteristic in both public and private educational environments, it has been strangely overlooked to help highlight its significance in many developing countries. In contrast, only a few studies focused on the concept of principals' leadership style and teachers' performance (Albugami, 2020; Chen, 2017). These studies mainly investigated the three important leadership styles: Democratic, Autocratic, and Laissez-Faire (Jay, 2014). However, no study so has examined the change-oriented leadership style in school settings. Thus, this research intends to address this gap to examine the effect of leadership style and the influence that is correlated with teachers and schools on their performance in public primary and secondary schools. Teachers' performance is a vital component of the students' outcome (Curricula and Co-Curricula) in the school, which heavily impacts countries' education. It has a chain of effects from childhood education to the country's economic development.

Therefore, the present research attempts to investigate the influences of principal leadership style and teachers' performance in government schools. Thus, this study contributes to the extent of the literature by investigating the role of three important leadership styles, Autocratic, Democratic, and Laissez-faire, in facilitating teachers' performance in government schools. Therefore, the concern of this investigation was to characterize the three types of leadership styles of principals that influence the teachers and school performance to bring novel contributions to various stakeholders. Hence, this study will be helpful to the school principals as well as to all the public members for emerging leadership practices in their organizations. It will have a favorable effect on the teachers' performance. It is concluded that the principals are a center pin for the continued improvement in education. This means the well-being of the societies can also be strengthened over a prolonged period.

In this regard, the study wanted to meet the two variables involved: leadership practices and teacher engagement in selected private schools in Gumaca, Quezon. Leadership practices can be different types like autocratic, dictatorship, democratic, laissez-faire, pace setter, paternal, and other leadership practices that can be employed to run the school effectively and efficiently.

In sum, the study will investigate or identify these types of leadership the principal or department heads apply to ensure that teachers are engaged in the selected private schools. These leadership practices determine the performance of the school and their commitment to total quality fulfillment for their learners or students. The teacher's engagement is the evidential matter of teachers/ empowerment in the school where a certain leadership practice was involved.

Research Questions

The study was conducted to determine the influence of principal leadership styles and practices in fostering teachers' development. Specifically, it will seek to answers to the following questions:

1. What are the leadership practices of selected Department Heads in terms of:
 - 1.1. charismatic leaders;
 - 1.2. innovative leaders;
 - 1.3. command and control leaders;
 - 1.4. laissez-faire leaders;
 - 1.5. pace setter leaders;
 - 1.6. servant leaders;
 - 1.7. situational leaders
2. What are the impacts of the leadership practices on teachers' engagement and motivation towards professional development activities in terms of:
 - 2.1. collaborative leadership;
 - 2.2. teacher collaboration;
 - 2.3. professional development;
 - 2.4. unity of purpose;
 - 2.5. collegial support;
 - 2.6. learning partnership;
3. Is there a significant relationship between the leadership practices of department heads and level of engagement of teachers?
4. Based on the study's findings, what professional development program can be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive method of research. The type of descriptive method to be used was the cross-sectional study. A cross-sectional study was a type of research design in which data was collected from many different individuals at a single point in time. In cross-sectional research, variables were observed without influencing them. Moreover, descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon. It can answer what, where, when, and how questions, but not why questions. A descriptive research design can use a wide variety of research methods to investigate one or more variables (Cantrell, 2019). The descriptive design also examined the phenomena as they existed (Edralin, 2020). The descriptive method assessed the level of school principal leadership on teachers' professional development. Using a descriptive design, the researcher conducted a survey. It evaluated the current trends, characteristics, cases, and follow-ups. This descriptive method was selected since the research would require non-experimental data treatment. The study also used this design since the best instrument that can be used is the questionnaire. The study transpired only for a maximum of one (1) year period, which fits a descriptive approach to research.

Respondents

The participants in this study include the secondary Junior High School teachers from Gumaca District within a specific geographic region. Purposive sampling will be used to identify participants who can provide rich and diverse perspectives. This may involve selecting principals recognized for their leadership in fostering teacher development and teachers from various grade levels and subject areas.

Procedure

Descriptive design was employed using the questionnaire as the main data gathering tool and with observation in the place of sustained interest. Before validation and use of the instrument, the researcher sought permission from the authors of the instrument to adapt or use the instrument for the study. A letter asking permission was sent thru email of the authors for their perusal and approval of the use of their instrument. The research instrument composed of two parts. The first part explained the school principal leadership in teachers' professional development. The second part discussed the impacts of school principal leadership on teachers' professional development. The questionnaire was prepared based on the literature or available standardized instrument fit for the study. The questionnaire had undergone two -step validation process. This comprised of content and concurrent and construct validity conducted through expert validation of three experts of the field – One Doctor, One Master Teacher, and One English teacher, and pilot testing of the instrument. Under Concurrent and Construct Validation, this involves dry run or pilot testing among at least thirty (30) respondents who answered the questionnaire. They did not form part of the actual data gathering.

In addition, the researcher first sought the approval of the research adviser. A rough draft of the paper and the questionnaire was prepared. The corrections and revisions were taken into consideration. After validation, the researcher coordinated with the schools and their school principals and Secondary Junior High Teachers regarding the plan to collect data from the respondents. The researcher distributed the questionnaire through the use of Google forms. Tallying and tabulations followed. The researcher made use of MS Excel and other database software statistics in measuring and analyzing the data.

Data Analysis

After gathering the responses from the respondents, necessary tallying and tabulations followed.

The study used the following statistical tools:

Frequency Count. This measured and analyzed the profile of the respondents with regard to their composition.

Percentage. This measured and analyzed the profile of the respondents with regard to their composition.

Weighted Mean. This measured the responses of the respondents with regard to bridging leadership competencies and performance of the PEAC Certified Schools in the CALABARZON Region.

Ethical Considerations

This study will adhere to strict ethical guidelines to ensure the well-being and privacy of participants. Prior to participating, all participants will be provided with an informed consent form that outlines the purpose of the study, data collection methods, and their rights as participants. Confidentiality of all data will be maintained throughout the research process and in any subsequent publications. Anonymity will be ensured by using pseudonyms for participants and schools in the reporting of the findings.

Results and Discussion

This part of the study shows the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the gathered data from the questionnaires answered by the respondents.

Leadership Practices of Selected Department Heads.

In Terms of Charismatic Leaders.

Table 1. *Leadership Practices of Selected Department Heads in Terms of Charismatic Leaders*

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
The department heads ...			
Provides inspiring and strategic management goals.	4.71	Excellent	5
Able to motivate by articulating effectively the importance of what organizational members are doing.	4.79	Excellent	4
Consistently generates new ideas for the future of the organization.	4.82	Excellent	3
Are exciting public speaker.	4.68	Excellent	6
Has vision and often brings up ideas about possibilities for the future.	4.89	Excellent	2
Seize new opportunities in order to achieve goals.	4.93	Excellent	1
Readily recognize new environmental opportunities (favorable physical and social conditions) that may facilitate achievement of organizational objectives.	4.57	Excellent	7
Composite Mean	4.77	Excellent	

As revealed in Table 1, the respondents answered that their department heads are excellent because they seize new opportunities in order to achieve goals which made the highest weighted mean of 4.93 and rank of 1. This implied that the department heads open up or find greater opportunities to achieve the targeted goals. According to Rhea Blanken (Blanken, 2013), common leadership styles like charismatic leaders are individuals who influences others through power of personality, acts energetically, and motivating others to move forward. Charismatic Leaders are leaders who possess certain qualities that inspire people and encourage devotion to a certain cause. Some charismatic leaders are Winston Churchill, Mahatma Gandhi, Mother Teresa.

In addition, the said group of respondents also replied that their department heads are excellent because they readily recognize new environmental opportunities (favorable physical and social conditions) that may facilitate achievement of organizational objectives which yielded the least weighted mean of 4.57 and least rank of 7. This revealed that the department heads have least preference towards the physical and social environments of the school. This posited that leadership is an acquired attribute that begins early in school and on the playground. As time goes on, education, jobs, and life experiences shape a leader's philosophy and psychology. How best to get the job done and work with other, how to set goals and objectives and manage their results, become a leader's winning formula for success. But over time, a leader may find that her winning formula is not producing the results it used to.

The composite mean of 4.77 implied that the department heads are excellent as charismatic leaders. This further implied that the respondents gave an excellent rating on the leadership practices of selected department heads. This is in line with Kouzes and Posner who have develop a straight forward series of leadership practices (behaviors): (i) Inspire the vision; (ii) Model the way; (iii) Challenge the Status Quo; (iv) Encourage the heart; (v) Enabling others to act. These five (5) practices line up well with leadership characteristics and traits. These behaviors are well received in most cultures and can be applied in a practical way to leadership development (Kouzes & Posner, 2009).

In Terms of Innovative Leaders.

As reflected in Table 2, the respondents replied that their department heads are excellent because they have the abilities and qualities in order to push for innovation in the activity field of the organization which got the highest weighted mean of 4.93 and rank of 1. This indicated that the department heads were employing process innovations to the schools.

Table 2. *Leadership Practices of Selected Department Heads in Terms of Innovative Leaders*

<i>Items</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
The department heads ...			
Are comfortable with uncertainty and have open mind.	4.82	Excellent	3
Are receptive to ideas from very different disciplines.	4.79	Excellent	4
Organize innovation into a disciplined process that is replicable.	4.75	Excellent	5.5
Have the tools and skills to pinpoint and manage the risks inherent in innovation.	4.75	Excellent	5.5
Are capable of adapting their behaviors to the requirements of certain situations that might appear.	4.86	Excellent	2
Have to be able to mobilize and motivate the team and make it aim towards "new."	4.68	Excellent	7
Have the abilities and qualities in order to push for innovation in the activity field of the organization.	4.93	Excellent	1
Composite Mean	4.80	Excellent	

According to Rhea Blanken (Blanken, 2013), innovative leaders are individuals who can grasp the entire situation and goes beyond the usual course of action. He/she can see what is not working and brings new thinking and action into play. Also, there is a time and place for all leadership style. New challenges require new leadership skills, behaviors, and ways of communicating. It is time to unlearn familiar leadership approach, recognize limitations, and adapt leadership style to become the leader one imagines to be. Leadership lives in how we think, not what we think.

Moreover, the said group of respondents answered that their department heads are excellent because they have to be able to mobilize and motivate the team and make it aim towards "new" which obtained the least weighted mean of 4.68 and least rank of 7. This implied that the department heads allow mobility and motivation among all the staff of the school for empowerment and productivity. This is in connection with the fact that leadership as a concept is difficult to describe. It has been a subject of thought and debate since the time of Aristotle and Plato. Diverse theories have evolved to explain various types of leadership styles. Although there is little consensus on single definition, leadership can be defined as a process designed to influence a group of individuals to work together to achieve a common goal.

The composite mean of 4.80 signified that the department heads are excellent as innovative leaders. This implied that the respondents gave an excellent rating on the leadership practices of selected department heads. This is in consonance with Blanchard and Hersey (2020) who developed a four (4) part model: (i) Directing - when an employee is new to a task or job; (ii) Coaching - the stage in which the employee is doing the task but tentatively and probably not perfectly; (iii) Supporting - employee knows the task but lacks some confidence; (iv) Delegating - employee is up to speed and can handle the job. This model has been appreciated for its practicality by some managers and supervisors. It is a quick tool that can be immediately applied and managers easily grasp the idea.

In Terms of Command-and-Control Leaders.

Table 3. *Leadership Practices of Selected Department Heads in Terms of Command-and-Control Leaders*

<i>Items</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
The department heads ...			
Decide based on the collective behavior in an organization.	4.64	Excellent	4
Apply to endeavors undertaken by collections of individuals and organizations of vastly different characteristics and sizes for many different purposes.	4.71	Excellent	3
Determine the bounds within which behavior(s) are to take place, not the specific behaviors themselves.	4.61	Excellent	5
Establish the conditions under which sense making and execution take place.	4.57	Excellent	6
Apply to all subsets of an enterprise, to the functions performed, to the levels of organizations, to the focus of the activity, whether strategic or tactical.	4.82	Excellent	1
Employ approaches that are appropriate for different sets of purposes or circumstances.	4.75	Excellent	2
Utilize approaches that may be taken by different sets of entities in an enterprise, may change over time.	4.54	Excellent	7
Composite Mean	4.66	Excellent	

As presented in Table 3, the respondents affirmed that their department heads are excellent because they apply to all subsets of an enterprise, to the functions performed, to the levels of organizations, to the focus of the activity, whether strategic or tactical which yielded the highest weighted mean of 4.82 and rank of 1. This showed that the department heads oversee the operational performance of the school. However, leadership of an educational institution is a chief responsibility of academic deans. The duties and responsibilities of academic deans are varied. Within the university hierarchy, deans have the ability to control information, accumulate and allocate resources, and assess the performance of their faculty and staff. The position of academic dean is unique because, unlike their corporate counterparts, academic deans act as both middle managers within the university and chief academic officers of their respective colleges (Del Favero, 2007).

Furthermore, the said group of respondents also answered that their department heads are excellent because they utilize approaches that may be taken by different sets of entities in an enterprise, may change over time which gained the least weighted mean of 4.54 and least rank of 7. This elicited that the department heads update themselves to a more advanced and sophisticated knowledge or information that can help the school towards performance excellence. Nevertheless, by virtue of their mid-level position, deans are in the center of controversy and debate; they play the role as college leader, university representative, consensus builder, mediator, and facilitator. The dean's role is multifaceted; as leaders, they must look in two directions, both as advocates of the college and for the university as a whole (Simons & Elen, 2007).

The composite mean of 4.66 concluded that the department heads are excellent as command and control leaders. This implied that the respondents gave an excellent rating on the leadership practices of selected department heads. This in connection with the fact that leadership has always been an issue among researchers. A number of researches have been done regarding the topic of leadership, but there are only a few studies that focused on leadership at school setting. The nexus of educational leadership appears to be shifting towards axis in two distinct ways. First, education growth and achievements are most dynamic within Asian countries relative to the former dominance of Europe and the Americas. Second, collaborative/institutional structural approaches to organizing governments and civic society within Asian contexts are being examined for the apparent success of such educational achievement (Dodgson 2007; Aggarwal and Koo 2008).

In Terms of Laissez-Faire Leaders.

As shown in Table 4, the respondents revealed that their department heads are excellent because they allow cooperative strategies for the members which made the highest weighted mean of 4.57 and rank of 1. This implied that the department heads apply social cooperation inside the school. Furthermore, academic deans are important stakeholders in the organization because they provide the leadership for the faculty as well as for other areas of the university. There is no formal leadership training for academic leaders because many deans rise from the ranks of faculty to the deanship position. Consequently, there are often variations in the leadership styles of academic deans arising from their background, years of experience, number of subordinates, education, and natural style (Trash, 2012).

Table 4. *Leadership Practices of Selected Department Heads in Terms of Laissez-Faire Leaders*

<i>Items</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
The department heads ...			
Should let members work out problems on their own.	4.25	Excellent	3.5
Are required staying out of the way of members as they do their work.	4.14	Very Good	5
Should allow members to appraise their own work.	4.43	Excellent	2
Should give members complete freedom to solve problems on their own.	4.25	Excellent	3.5
Prefer little input from the leader.	3.89	Very Good	6
Leave members alone.	3.18	Good	7
Allow cooperative strategies for the members.	4.57	Excellent	1
Composite Mean	4.10	Very Good	

On the other hand, the said group of respondents replied that their department heads are very good because they leave members alone which obtained the least weighted mean of 3.18 and least rank of 7. This posited that the department heads showed least preference in leaving the members in the schools alone. This means that they instituted social interactions and greater social intelligence in the schools. Since academic deans operate at the nexus of the executive branch of colleges and universities, the dean's role is critical to the success of the institution. Therefore, the academic dean's leadership style has a direct impact on the school's success (Trash, 2012).

The composite mean of 4.10 signified that the department heads are very good as laissez faire leaders. This implied that the respondents gave a very good rating on the leadership practices of selected department heads. This is supported by the idea and evidences that there are other sex-related differences that may be more important. These are the differences in leaders' values and attitudes. This aspect of leaders' psychology helps us understand their goals and motivations - what they want to achieve as leaders. Cross-national surveys have shown that leaders place more emphasis on the social values of benevolence and universalism. Benevolence refers to "preservation and enhancement of the welfare of people with whom one is in frequent personal contact" and universalism to the "understanding, appreciation, tolerance, and protection for the welfare of all people and for nature".

In Terms of Pace Setter Leaders.

As gleaned in Table 5, the respondents assessed that their department heads are excellent because they usually reach the high standard target which garnered the highest weighted mean of 4.29 and rank of 1. This showed that the department heads upgrade their knowledge to attain higher standards of performance in the schools. According to Rhea Blanken (Blanken, 2013), Pace Setter Leaders are individuals who set high performance standards for self and the group. He/she knows that when staff are self-motivated and highly skilled, he can embrace new projects and move with speed.

However, the said group of respondents perceived that their department heads are very good because they replace subordinates by those who can achieve the results on time which got the least weighted mean of 2.75 and least rank of 7. This showed that the department heads least preferred this indicator not to be strict with the performance and time management of the people inside the schools. This is

in line with the study conducted by Madden (2011) who reviews social psychological and organizational development literature on gender stereotypes and leadership style and effectiveness and explores its relevance for leadership in higher education. Implications of the dichotomous stereotypes of “friendly vs. competent” and “agentive vs. communal” frame a discussion of social psychological research on how stereotypes affect perceptions of leaders.

Table 5. *Leadership Practices of Selected Department Heads in Terms of Pace Setter Leaders*

<i>Items</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
The department heads ...			
Feel overwhelmed by the pacesetter's demand for excellence.	4.04	Very Good	2
Set a standard that are extremely high.	3.79	Very Good	3
Usually reach the high standard target.	4.29	Excellent	1
Are obsessed with doing things better and faster than everyone.	3.43	Very Good	4.5
Expect subordinate to excel in the same way as he does.	3.43	Very Good	4.5
Replace subordinates by those who can achieve the results on time.	2.75	Good	7
Make feedback practically no-existent.	3.21	Good	6
Composite Mean	3.56	Very Good	

The composite means of 3.56 implied that the department heads are very good as pace setter leaders. This implied that the respondents gave a very good rating on the leadership practices of selected department heads. Consequently, the distributed view of leadership is responsible from a shift of focus in that the emphasis is no longer on school principals and other formal and informal leaders but on a web of stakeholders and their situations (Spillane & Diamond, 2007).

In Terms of Servant Leaders.

Table 6. *Leadership Practices of Selected Department Heads in Terms of Servant Leaders*

<i>Items</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
The department heads ...			
Give others the responsibility to make important decisions about their own jobs.	4.43	Excellent	5.5
Encourage others to handle important work decisions on their own.	4.43	Excellent	5.5
Have a thorough understanding of the organization and its goals.	4.75	Excellent	2
Give others the freedom to handle difficult situations in the way they feel is best.	4.46	Excellent	3.5
Provide others with work experiences that enable them to develop new skills.	4.89	Excellent	1
Sacrifice his/her own interests to meet others' needs.	4.32	Excellent	7
Can recognize when others are feeling down without asking them.	4.46	Excellent	3.5
Composite Mean	4.54	Excellent	

As stated in Table 6, the respondents reported that their department heads are excellent because they provide others with work experiences that enable them to develop new skills which gained the highest weighted mean of 4.89 and rank of 1. This indicated that the department heads acted as an exemplary leader towards their subordinates in the schools. According to Rhea Blanken (Blanken, 2013), servant leaders are persons who put service to others before self-interest. He stays out of limelight and let the team accept credit for results.

Additionally, the said group of respondents displayed that their department heads are excellent because they sacrifice their own interests to meet others' needs which had the least weighted mean of 4.32 and least rank of 7. This elicited that the department head have least preference in sacrificing their own interests since this may be hard on their parts. At the school, teachers may be considered to engage in distributed leadership practice when, for instance, they collaborate in an attempt to take action regarding specific problems. A distributed perspective can be viewed as a conceptual framework for investigating school leadership and management. It involves two aspects: the leader plus aspect (who) and the practice aspect (how). The leader-plus aspect acknowledges that the work of leading schools involves multiple individuals and is not restricted to those at the top of the organizational hierarchy or those assigned formal leadership duties. In this framework, leadership practice is the outcome of the interaction of school leaders, followers, and their situations (Spillane, Hunt, & Healy, 2008).

The composite mean of 4.54 indicated that the department heads are excellent as servant leaders. This implied that the respondents gave an excellent rating on the leadership practices of selected department heads. According to Gronn (2010, p. 325), a distributed view of organizational activities and tasks is linked to a new form of the division of labor in organizations, in which “the authorship and the scope of the activities to be performed have to be redefined to encompass pluralities of agents whose actions dovetail or mesh to express new patterns of interdependent relations.”

In Terms of Situational Leaders.

As displayed in Table 7, the respondents stated that their department heads are excellent because they are willing to take responsibility for directing their own behavior which made the highest weighted mean of 4.68 and rank of 1. This showed that the department heads exert responsibility and accountability inside the school. This is supported by the idea that Ethical attitudes are also potentially important for leadership. Meta-analyses of studies on ethical beliefs and decision-making have shown that women are more likely than

men to support ethical business practices (Harrison & Treviño, 2010). Consistent with this trend, the representation of women on corporate boards related to more positive social outcomes and greater corporate responsibility, especially through companies not engaging in negative, unethical business practices (Boulouta, 2012).

Table 7. *Leadership Practices of Selected Department Heads in Terms of Situational Leaders*

<i>Items</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
The department heads ...			
Are willing to take responsibility for directing their own behavior.	4.68	Excellent	1
Reduce task behavior and increase relationship behavior.	4.29	Excellent	3
Focus on the appropriateness of effectiveness of leadership styles according to the task-relevant readiness of the follower.	4.39	Excellent	2
Spend more time directing the person in what to do and how, when, and where to do it, than providing socioemotional support and reinforcement.	4.07	Very Good	4
Develop the follower slowly, using a little less task behavior and a little more relationship behavior as the follower increases in readiness.	3.68	Very Good	7
Reduce a little of the structure or direction (task behavior) by giving the follower an opportunity to assume some increased responsibility.	3.82	Very Good	6
Reinforce the behavior with increases in relationship behavior.	4.04	Very Good	5
Composite Mean	4.14	Very Good	

On the contrary, the said group of respondents acknowledged that their department heads are very good because they develop the follower slowly, using a little less task behavior and a little more relationship behavior as the follower increases in readiness which got the least weighted mean of 3.68 and least rank of 7. This revealed that the department heads least preferred this indicator for it may be hard on the part of them to train the people inside the schools. Likewise, the research on mandated women village council leaders in India found these women less likely to pay bribes than their male counterparts, in other words, they were less corrupt (Beaman et al., 2009). Finally, at the national level, political scientists have associated larger representations of women in parliaments with less political corruption. Therefore, the effects of sex-related values, attitudes, and ethical tendencies deserve more attention.

The composite mean of 4.14 supported that the department heads are very good as situational leaders. This implied that the respondents gave a very good rating on the leadership practices of selected department heads. There are other sex-related differences that may be more important. These are the differences in leaders' values and attitudes. This aspect of leaders' psychology helps us understand their goals and motivations - what they want to achieve as leaders. Cross-national surveys have shown that women place more emphasis on the social values of benevolence and universalism. Benevolence refers to "preservation and enhancement of the welfare of people with whom one is in frequent personal contact" and universalism to the "understanding, appreciation, tolerance, and protection for the welfare of all people and for nature". Other researchers have found that, compared with men, women endorse social values that promote others' welfare. Women endorse socially compassionate social policies and more practices that uphold marriage, the family, and organized religion. Although generalizability of such findings is not well established, there are numerous indications that they probably do. For example, as members of legislative bodies, women are more likely than their male colleagues to advocate for changes that promote the interests of women, children, and families and that support public welfare in areas such as health care and education (Kunovich & Hughes 2007, Wangnerud, 2009).

Impact of the Leadership Practices on Teachers' Engagement and Motivation Towards Professional Development Activities.

In Terms of Collaborative Leadership

Table 8. *Impact of the Leadership Practices on Teachers' Engagement and Motivation Towards Professional Development Activities in Terms of Collaborative Leadership*

<i>Items</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Leaders value teachers' ideas.	4.62	Excellent	7
Leaders in the school trust the professional judgments of teachers.	4.96	Excellent	1
Leaders take time to praise teachers that perform well.	4.79	Excellent	3
Teachers are involved in the decision-making process.	4.61	Excellent	8
Leaders in our school facilitate teachers working together.	4.64	Excellent	6
Teachers are kept informed on current issues in the school.	4.93	Excellent	2
My involvement in policy or decision making is taken seriously.	4.75	Excellent	4
Teachers are rewarded for experimenting with new ideas and techniques.	4.71	Excellent	5
Leaders support risk-taking and innovation in teaching.	3.93	Very Good	11
Administrators protect instruction and planning time.	4.46	Excellent	9
Teachers are encouraged to share ideas.	4.32	Excellent	10
Composite Mean	4.62	Excellent	

As gleaned in Table 8, the respondents declared that excellent leaders in the school trust the professional judgments of teachers which made the highest weighted mean of 4.96 and the highest rank of 1. This posited that the school give high regard to teachers' professional judgment. This is backed up by the fact that school principals play a pivotal role in shaping the school environment and influencing

teacher behavior. Understanding various leadership styles can provide valuable insights into how principals can foster teacher growth. One of the prominent leadership theories include: Transformational Leadership: This style focuses on inspiring and motivating teachers to achieve their full potential. Transformational leaders articulate a clear vision for the school, promote innovation, and empower teachers to take ownership of their professional development (Leithwood, 1999).

In addition, the said group of respondents that all good leaders support risk-taking and innovation in teaching which made the least weighted mean of 3.93 and the least rank of 11. The school heads gave least preference to applying risk-taking and innovative teaching which they may be encountering somewhat a problem in utilizing such approaches or methodologies. Several studies have explored the relationship between principal leadership and teacher PD. For example, Leithwood, Seashore, and Wahlstrom (2004) found that strong instructional leadership practices, such as providing feedback and facilitating collaborative learning, positively influenced teacher participation in PD activities. Additionally, Louis and Leithwood (2007) highlighted the importance of principal commitment to PD, emphasizing that principals who actively support and value professional learning create a more receptive environment for teacher growth.

The composite mean of 4.62 concluded that collaborative leadership has an excellent impact of the leadership practices on teachers engagement and motivation towards professional development activities. This implied that the respondents gave an excellent rating on the impacts of leadership practices on teachers' engagement and motivation towards professional development activities. However, some studies also identify limitations in current practices. Fullan (2000) critiques "one-size-fits-all" PD models and argues for a more personalized approach that considers individual teacher needs and preferences. Furthermore, several studies highlight the need for ongoing support for teachers beyond initial PD workshops, emphasizing the importance of coaching, mentoring, and opportunities for teachers to share best practices (Guskey, 2002; Lopez et al., 2006).

In Terms of Teacher Collaboration

Table 9. *Impact of the Leadership Practices on Teachers' Engagement and Motivation Towards Professional Development Activities in Terms of Teacher Collaboration*

<i>Items</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Teachers have opportunities for dialogue and planning across grades and subjects.	4.86	Excellent	1
Teachers spend considerable time planning together.	4.64	Excellent	2
Teachers take time to observe each other teaching.	4.14	Very Good	6
Teachers are generally aware of what other teachers are teaching.	4.46	Excellent	4.5
Teachers work together to develop and evaluate programs and projects.	4.54	Excellent	3
Teaching practice disagreements are voiced openly and discussed.	4.46	Excellent	4.5
Composite Mean	4.52	Excellent	

As seen in Table 9, the respondents asserted that teachers have excellent opportunities for dialogue and planning across grades and subjects which got the highest weighted mean of 4.86 and the highest rank of 1. This implied that the teachers were given enough time for preparation and lesson planning. This is linked with the performance in the school with regard to teachers' engagement. The term performance has been defined differently by different scholars basing on the perspective from which they approach it. According to summer matter and Siegel (2019), it may imply efficiency, economy, results, or return (profits) on investment.

However, the said group of respondents affirmed that teachers are very good in taking time to observe each other teaching which obtained the least weighted mean of 4.14 and the least rank of 6. This indicated that the teachers in the school apply peer or team teaching. Some scholars have viewed performance as the behavioral aspect that defines the way in which organizations, teams and individual employees get work done; it is the output record of a specific job function or activity at a given time (Armstrong, 2013). Performance is the degree to which an employee and organizational goals are met (Feng, 2020). It comprises both behavior and outcomes (Armstrong, 2013; Feng, 2010).

The composite mean of 4.52 affirmed that teacher collaboration has an excellent impact of the leadership practices on teachers engagement and motivation towards professional development activities. This implied that the respondents gave an excellent rating on the impacts of leadership practices on teachers' engagement and motivation towards professional development activities. This is in line with the way teachers were motivated to work as a team. Behavior comes from the worker who transforms performance from abstraction into action leading to outcome (Kalyani, 2016). Feng (2010) identified three directions from which performance can be viewed, that is, results oriented performance, conduct oriented performance and the integration of conduct and result oriented performance. Several researchers throughout the evolution of organizational theory have focused on the best way to measure individual and organizational performance and realized that it is a dynamic concept that varies across geographical space, time and scholarly schools of thought (Waititu, F. et. al, 2017).

In Terms of Professional Development

As written in Table 10, the respondents declared that teachers are excellent in regularly seeking ideas from seminars, colleagues, and conferences; pprofessional development is valued by the faculty which made the highest equal weighted means of 4.86 and the highest similar ranks of 1.5 This implied that the teachers valued their competence and professional/career development through trainings and

seminars. On the contrary, behaviour comes from the worker who transforms performance from abstraction into action leading to outcome (Kalyani, 2016). Feng (2010) identified three directions from which performance can be viewed, that is, results oriented performance, conduct oriented performance and the integration of conduct and result oriented performance.

Table 10. *Impact of the Leadership Practices on Teachers' Engagement and Motivation Towards Professional Development Activities in Terms of Professional Development*

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Teachers utilize professional networks to obtain information and resources for classroom instruction.	4.68	Excellent	4.5
Teachers regularly seek ideas from seminars, colleagues, and conferences.	4.86	Excellent	1.5
Professional development is valued by the faculty.	4.86	Excellent	1.5
Teachers maintain a current knowledge base about the learning process.	4.68	Excellent	4.5
The faculty values school improvement.	4.79	Excellent	3
Composite Mean	4.77	Excellent	

As written in Table 10, the respondents declared that teachers are excellent in regularly seeking ideas from seminars, colleagues, and conferences; professional development is valued by the faculty which made the highest equal weighted means of 4.86 and the highest similar ranks of 1.5 This implied that the teachers valued their competence and professional/career development through trainings and seminars. On the contrary, behaviour comes from the worker who transforms performance from abstraction into action leading to outcome (Kalyani, 2016). Feng (2010) identified three directions from which performance can be viewed, that is, results oriented performance, conduct oriented performance and the integration of conduct and result oriented performance.

Additionally, the said group of respondents agreed that teachers are also excellent in utilizing professional networks to obtain information and resources for classroom instruction; and teachers excellently maintain current knowledge base about the learning process which garnered the least equal weighted means of 4.68 and the least ranks of 4.5. This implied that the teachers develop connections for the benefit of the teaching and learning process through learning partnership programs. Several researchers throughout the evolution of organizational theory have focused on the best way to measure individual and organizational performance and realized that it is a dynamic concept that varies across geographical space, time and scholarly schools of thought (Waititu, F. et. al, 2017).

The composite mean of 4.77 signified that professional development has an excellent impact of the leadership practices on teachers engagement and motivation towards professional development activities. This implied that the respondents gave an excellent rating on the impacts of leadership practices on teachers' engagement and motivation towards professional development activities.

Moreover, performance and its crucial dimensions change and differs over time and space depending on the relations between inputs, activity, output and effect. Over 300 papers from 14 journals were analyzed by Summer matter and Siegel (2019), they discovered that the word performance as applied in management has several dimensions, subsumed terms and categorizations. The categorization shows that performance is a multi-dimensional concept that is applicable to governments, government agencies, policies, projects, processes, programmes, industrial establishments, the private sector and individual employees.

In Terms of Unity of Purpose

Table 11. *Impact of the Leadership Practices on Teachers' Engagement and Motivation Towards Professional Development Activities in Terms of Unity of Purpose*

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Teachers support the mission of the school.	4.95	Excellent	4
The school mission provides a clear sense of direction for teachers.	4.96	Excellent	2
Teachers understand the mission of the school.	4.96	Excellent	2
The school mission statement reflects the values of the community.	4.96	Excellent	2
Teaching performance reflects the mission of the school.	4.93	Excellent	5
Composite Mean	4.95	Excellent	

As discussed in Table 11, the respondents reported that the school mission excellently provides a clear sense of direction for teachers, teachers excellently understand the mission of the school, and the school mission statement excellently reflects the values of the community which garnered the highest equal weighted means of 4.96 and the highest ranks of 2. This indicated that the teachers apply the mission of the school and their personal life or growth as a person and its purpose in their life's philosophies. Their findings revealed that the most common dimensions of performance are outcome, output, efficiency, requirements, input, effectiveness, quality but there is not a one size fits all definition of performance in the development of the principles and practice of management. Performance, therefore, entails a mixture of doing a job effectively and efficiently, with a minimum degree of employee created disruptions (Decenzo and Robbins, 2018).

Moreover, the said group of respondents agreed that teaching performance excellently reflects the mission of the school which presented the least weighted mean of 4.93 and the least rank of 5. This implied that the school linked with the community and how the teachers impart their knowledge to the students and the entire community. It was further asserted that teachers' performance is the extent to which the teacher achieves school objectives through lesson preparations which involve making schemes of work, lesson plans, record

of work done, preparing and using learners' registers, actual classroom teaching, assessment and evaluation of the learners, attending staff meetings, management of learners' discipline, involvement in co-curricular activities, counselling and guidance (Umar, 2018).

The composite mean of 4.95 concluded that unity of purpose has an excellent impact of the leadership practices on teachers engagement and motivation towards professional development activities. This implied that the respondents gave an excellent rating on the impacts of leadership practices on teachers' engagement and motivation towards professional development activities.

Also, Katarasibwa (2016) viewed teacher performance to mean the process by which the teacher is able to realize a maximum requirements level of their job in an effort to fulfil the school objectives. Umar (2018) defined teacher performance as the overall classroom management, effective teaching, motivation to teach, school and classroom punctuality as well as good team work.

In Terms of Collegial Support

Table 12. *Impact of the Leadership Practices on Teachers' Engagement and Motivation Towards Professional Development Activities in Terms of Collegial Support*

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Teachers trust each other.	4.82	Excellent	3
Teachers are willing to help out whenever there is a problem.	4.86	Excellent	1.5
Teachers' ideas are valued by other teachers.	4.86	Excellent	1.5
Teachers work cooperatively in groups.	4.75	Excellent	4
Composite Mean	4.82	Excellent	

As reported in Table 12, the respondents asserted that teachers are excellently willing to help out whenever there is a problem, and teachers' ideas are excellently valued by other teachers which made the highest equal weighted means of 4.86 and the highest ranks of 1.5 This implied that the teachers have initiative to help in the school during adverse situations and their ideas were highly valued. According to Umar (2018), he outlined five constructs of teachers, performance: timely scheming of work; timely lesson planning; lesson delivery/actual teaching; maintenance of records of work covered and teachers' physical presence in school.

In addition, the said group of respondents replied that teachers excellently work cooperatively in groups which obtained the least weighted mean of 4.75 and the least rank of 4. This posited that there is cooperation exerted to one another for the betterment of the schools. According to Abwalla (2014), teachers' performance refers to identification with, and involvement in the teaching occupation. He argued that teacher performance is considered as the act of scheming, lesson planning, and assessment of students through giving tests, exercises and participation in co-curricular activities of the schools. He identified four dimensions of teacher performance as follows: lesson plan preparation, assessing students, involvement in co-curricular activity and syllables completion.

The composite mean of 4.82 concluded that collegial support has an excellent impact of the leadership practices on teachers engagement and motivation towards professional development activities. This implied that the respondents gave an excellent rating on the impacts of leadership practices on teachers' engagement and motivation towards professional development activities. Obilade (2019) sees teacher performance as the duties performed by a teacher at a particular period in the school system in achieving educational goals whereas, (Akinyemi 1993; Okeniyi, 2015) defined it as the ability of teachers to combine relevant inputs for the enhancement of teaching and learning processes.

In Terms of Learning Partnership.

Table 13. *Impact of the Leadership Practices on Teachers' Engagement and Motivation Towards Professional Development Activities in Terms of Learning Partnership*

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Teachers and parents have common expectations for student performance.	4.39	Excellent	4
Parents trust teachers' professional judgments.	4.64	Excellent	3
Teachers and parents communicate frequently about student performance.	4.68	Excellent	1.5
Students generally accept responsibility for their schooling, for example they engage mentally in class and complete homework assignments.	4.68	Excellent	1.5
Composite Mean	4.60	Excellent	

As given in Table 13, the respondents acknowledged that teachers and parents communicate frequently about student performance, and students generally accept responsibility for their schooling, for example they engage mentally in class and complete homework assignments, both rated as excellent, which got the highest equal weighted means of 4.68 and the highest ranks of 1. This elicited that the teachers and parents also work together for high learning outcomes and high academic performance. However, Meindl (2015) argued that teachers' performance is determined by the worker's level of participation in the day to day running of the organization.

In addition, the said group of respondents agreed that teachers and parents have excellent common expectations for student performance which gained the least weighted mean of 4.39 and the least rank of 4. This indicated that the teachers experience the same or parallel experiences with regard to student performance. Adepoju, (2016) supports the argument by stating that variables of teachers' performance such as effective teaching, lesson note preparation, effective use of scheme of work, effective supervision, monitoring of

students' work and disciplinary ability are virtues which teachers should uphold effectively in the school system. In this regard, the teachers' performance could be measured through annual report of his/ her activities in terms of performance in teaching, lesson preparation, and lesson presentation, mastery of subject matter, competence, teachers' commitment to job and extracurricular activities.

The composite mean of 4.60 implied that learning partnership has an excellent impact of the leadership practices on teachers engagement and motivation towards professional development activities. This implied that the respondents gave an excellent rating on the impacts of leadership practices on teachers' engagement and motivation towards professional development activities.

Other areas of assessment include effective leadership, supervision of students' work; motivation, class control and discipline of the students are the virtues that teachers should uphold effectively in general secondary schools (Adepoju, 2016).

Relationship Between the Leadership Practices of Department Heads and Level of Engagement of Teachers.

Table 14.1. *Relationship Between the Leadership Practices of Department Heads and Level of Engagement of Teachers*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Charismatic Leaders versus Level of Engagement of Teachers:				
Collaborative Leadership	0.64	0.00018	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Teacher Collaboration	0.22	0.25149	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Professional Development	0.67	0.00007	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Unity of Purpose	0.81	1.00E-7	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Collegial Support	0.36	0.05508	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Learning Partnership	0.02	0.91798	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Innovative Leaders versus Level of Engagement of Teachers:				
Collaborative Leadership	0.63	0.00025	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Teacher Collaboration	0.39	0.03649	Reject Ho	Significant
Professional Development	0.76	1.73E-6	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Unity of Purpose	0.76	1.73E-6	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Collegial Support	0.44	0.01692	Reject Ho	Significant
Learning Partnership	0.08	0.67995	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Command and Control Leaders versus Level of Engagement of Teachers:				
Collaborative Leadership	0.69	0.00003	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Teacher Collaboration	0.41	0.02718	Reject Ho	Significant
Professional Development	0.61	0.00044	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Unity of Purpose	0.80	1.90E-7	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Collegial Support	0.48	0.00841	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Learning Partnership	0.14	0.46886	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Laissez-Faire Leaders versus Level of Engagement of Teachers:				
Collaborative Leadership	-0.08	0.67995	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Teacher Collaboration	0.01	0.95894	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Professional Development	0.21	0.27422	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Unity of Purpose	0.39	0.03649	Reject Ho	Significant
Collegial Support	0.34	0.07114	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Learning Partnership	0.13	0.50150	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Table 14.1 shows the relationship between the leadership practices of Department Heads and level of engagement of Teachers. As to Charismatic Leaders as compared with Collaborative Leadership (p-value = 0.00018), Professional Development (p-value = 0.00007), and Unity of Purpose (p-value = 0.00007), the p-values were less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There exists a significant relationship between the leadership practices of Department Heads and level of engagement of Teachers.

In accordance with Innovative Leaders as compared with Collaborative Leadership (p-value = 0.00025), Teacher Collaboration (p-value = 0.03649), Professional Development (p-value = 0.000173), Unity of Purpose (p-value = 0.000173), and Collegial Support (p-value = 0.01692), the p-values were less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There exists a significant relationship between the leadership practices of Department Heads and level of engagement of Teachers.

As regards with Command-and-Control Leaders as compared with Collaborative Leadership (p-value = 0.00003), Teachers' Collaboration (p-value = 0.02718), Professional Development (p-value = 0.00044), Unity of Purpose (p-value = 0.000019), and Collegial Support (p-value = 0.00841), the p-values were less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There exists a significant relationship between the leadership practices of Department Heads and level of engagement of Teachers.

And, when it comes to Laissez-Faire Leaders as compared with Unity of Purpose (p-value = 0.03649), the p-value was less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There exists a significant relationship between the leadership practices of Department Heads and level of engagement of Teachers.

Table 14.2. *Relationship Between the Leadership Practices of Department Heads and Level of Engagement of Teachers*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Pace Setter Leaders versus Level of Engagement of Teachers:				
Collaborative Leadership	-0.04	0.83678	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Teacher Collaboration	0.45	0.01431	Reject Ho	Significant
Professional Development	-0.17	0.37797	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Unity of Purpose	0.09	0.64244	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Collegial Support	0.24	0.20984	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Learning Partnership	0.03	0.87723	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Servant Leaders versus Level of Engagement of Teachers:				
Collaborative Leadership	0.45	0.01431	Reject Ho	Significant
Teacher Collaboration	0.83	3.00E-8	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Professional Development	0.12	0.53523	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Unity of Purpose	0.36	0.05508	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Collegial Support	0.59	0.00076	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Learning Partnership	-0.01	0.95894	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Situational Leaders versus Level of Engagement of Teachers:				
Collaborative Leadership	0.32	0.09059	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Teacher Collaboration	0.39	0.03649	Reject Ho	Significant
Professional Development	0.24	0.20984	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Unity of Purpose	0.08	0.67995	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Collegial Support	0.27	0.15663	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Learning Partnership	0.22	0.25149	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Table 14.2 shows the relationship between the leadership practices of Department Heads and level of engagement of Teachers. According to Pace Setter Leaders as compared with Teacher Collaboration (p-value = 0.01431), the p-value was less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There exists a significant relationship between the leadership practices of Department Heads and level of engagement of Teachers. In terms of Servant Leaders as compared with Collaborative Leadership (p-value = 0.01431), Teacher Collaboration (p-value = 0.00003), and Collegial Support (p-value = 0.00076), the p-values were less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There exists a significant relationship between the leadership practices of Department Heads and level of engagement of Teachers. Along with Situational Leaders as compare with Teacher Collaboration (p-value = 0.03649), the p-value was less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. There exists a significant relationship between the leadership practices of Department Heads and level of engagement of Teachers.

Proposed Program Based on the Result of the Study

Rationale of the Program

The professional development program covered the applications of the leadership practices which were those that fit the school and those that were applicable to certain situations or circumstances. Upon applying the leadership practices, this program provided the impacts of those leadership practices being applied and conducted by this study for global or at-par school performance with quality educational services. This program evaluated the situation or condition in the study by citing its findings and results.

This study revealed that the leadership practices by the respondents towards selected department heads were excellent as employed or applied in the schools. This is reflected on Innovative Leaders where the department heads have the abilities and qualities in order to push for innovation in the activity field of the organization. When it comes to Charismatic Leaders, the department heads seize new opportunities in order to achieve goals. And, as referred to Command and Control Leaders, the department heads apply to all subsets of an enterprise, to the functions performed, to the levels of organizations, to the focus of the activity, whether strategic or tactical.

In addition, there is an excellent impact of leadership practices of the department heads towards teachers' engagement and motivation as can be observed in the school performance. This can be inferred to Unity of Purpose where the school mission provides a clear sense of direction for teachers, teachers understand the mission of the school, and the school mission statement reflects the values of the community. Along with Collegial Support, it indicated: teachers are willing to help out whenever there is a problem and teachers' ideas are valued by other teachers. And, in terms of Professional Development, it exemplified that teachers regularly seek ideas from seminars, colleagues, and conferences and professional development is valued by the faculty. Lastly, in general, there is no significant relationship between leadership practices and impacts of leadership practices on teachers' engagement and motivation. However, each leadership practice has at least one but at most five of the teachers' engagement indicator exhibiting significant relationship between leadership practices and its impacts to teachers' engagement and motivation.

Objectives of the Program

This program aims to address and to give immediate attention to the following based on the lowest indicators or those that were given lowest response in the study:

To replace subordinates by those who can achieve the results on time for efficiency and effectiveness of teachers or subordinates.

To require teachers to take time to observe each other teaching inside the classroom in the schools.

To disseminate information about the leadership practices and their would-be impact to teachers' engagement and motivation in order to achieve performance excellent, continual school improvement process, quality educational services, and better or (should we say) at-par or high school performance.

To implement the Professional Development Program.

Content of the Program

The following content will accrue to the program and hence to the schools:

Accomplishment Report Program. This will be conducted or implemented to the subordinates to accomplish the results or everything on time and with higher efficiency and effectiveness in the workplace.

Peer- and Team-Teaching Program. This will be accrued to the joint efforts of the teachers through peer and team teaching inside the school to ensure mastery of the subject matter and realistic applications of the knowledge that they will teach to their students.

Research Conference Program. This will be organized for the benefit of this research during which time that the school will hold thesis defenses or research for a colloquium to include this research in the conference or as basis in the thesis defense for the sole purpose of disseminating the information here stated in this research, or to a journal publication when there is a chance.

Implementing Guidelines Program. This will be crafted or enacted for the sole purpose of sharing the information of this study and to update the school of what best leadership practice can be applied or employed and the impacts of which.

Scope of the Program

The program covered only two important components: (1) The Best Leadership Practice and (2) the Impactful Leadership Practice to Teachers' Engagement and Motivation. With this program, it included the contents for consideration of the schools and the beneficiaries of this research on how to utilize the information generated or produced by this study for application and implementation.

Conclusions

Based on the findings derived, the following conclusions were drawn:

The leadership practices by the respondents towards selected department heads were excellent as employed or applied in the schools. This is reflected on Innovative Leaders where the department heads have the abilities and qualities in order to push for innovation in the activity field of the organization. When it comes to Charismatic Leaders, the department heads seize new opportunities in order to achieve goals. And, as referred to Command and Control Leaders, the department heads apply to all subsets of an enterprise, to the functions performed, to the levels of organizations, to the focus of the activity, whether strategic or tactical.

There is an excellent impact of leadership practices of the department heads towards teachers' engagement and motivation as can be observed in the school performance. This can be inferred to Unity of Purpose where the school mission provides a clear sense of direction for teachers, teachers understand the mission of the school, and the school mission statement reflects the values of the community. Along with Collegial Support, it indicated: teachers are willing to help out whenever there is a problem and teachers' ideas are valued by other teachers. And, in terms of Professional Development, it exemplified that teachers regularly seek ideas from seminars, colleagues, and conferences and professional development is valued by the faculty.

In general, there is no significant relationship between leadership practices and impacts of leadership practices on teachers' engagement and motivation. However, each leadership practice has at least one but at most five of the teachers' engagement indicator exhibiting significant relationship between leadership practices and its impacts to teachers' engagement and motivation.

The professional development program covered the applications of the leadership practices which were those that fit the school and those that were applicable to certain situations or circumstances. Upon applying the leadership practices, this program provided the impacts of those leadership practices being applied and conducted by this study for global or at-par school performance with quality educational services.

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following were recommended:

Replace subordinates by those who can achieve the results on time for efficiency and effectiveness of teachers or subordinates.

Require teachers to take time to observe each other teaching inside the classroom in the schools.

Disseminate information about the leadership practices and their would-be impact to teachers' engagement and motivation in order to achieve performance excellence, continual school improvement process, quality educational services, and better or (should we say) at-par or high school performance.

Implement the Professional Development Program.

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